

Supplement for

Heterogeneous photochemistry of dicarboxylic acids on mineral dust

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Arizona test dust composition

According to the manufacturer's characterization datasheet, it is composed of various oxides of crustal elements, mainly, silicon and aluminium. The lot used in this work has been characterized by Inductive Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) analysis confirming the chemical composition provided by the manufacturer (Dupart, 2012), **Table S 1**.

Table S 1: Comparison of the Chemical composition of ATD.

Chemical composition of major oxides (% wt.)

	ATD Manufacturer	ICP- IOS IRCELYON (Dupart, 2012)
SiO ₂	68.0 - 76.0	77.2
Al ₂ O ₃	10.0 - 15.0	8.13
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.0 - 5.0	2.00
CaO	2.0 - 5.0	2.38
K ₂ O	2.0 - 5.0	2.41
Na ₂ O	2.0 - 4.0	1.40
MgO	1.0 - 2.0	0.66
TiO ₂	0.5 - 1.0	0.33

LC-MS Protocol Details

Table S 2: Volume of reconstituted extract sample used for each acid LC-MS analysis. Sample's dilution volume for each acid was adjusted to avoid the instrument's saturation.

Acid	V _{sample} for LC (μL)
Glutaric (C ₅)	25
Adipic (C ₆)	40
Pimelic (C ₇)	40
Suberic (C ₈)	40

HESI – Negative Mode

The mass spectrometer was operated in full-scan mode with a scanning range from 50 to 750 m/z and a resolution of 140,000 at m/z 200. Electrospray ionization was performed in negative mode using HESI voltage of 3.0 kV, sheath gas flow rate of 40 arbitrary units (a.u.), auxiliary gas flow rate of 25 a.u, capillary temperature of 350 °C and heater temperature of 250 °C. The Q-Exactive mass spectrometer was calibrated externally every day by direct infusion of a sodium acetate solution (2 mM in H₂O/CH₃CN 1/1 v/v) to reach mass accuracies below 2 ppm.

PTR-ToF-MS

Instrument Parameters

Source current was 4.6 mA; source voltage: 113 V; source outlet voltage: 83 V and source valve opening at 34 % with a flow of 7.5 sccm of water vapor. Transmission efficiency curves for our instrument were obtained using a calibrated TO-14 aromatic mixture (Restek).

Additional Results – Dicarboxylic acids gas-phase products

Figure S. 1: On the left, mixing ratios time profiles, and on the right, the net product formation for 1 h irradiation for selected gas phase products observed by PTR-ToF-MS for irradiated ATD films coated with (a) Succinic acid (C₄), (b) Pimelic acid (C₇), and (c) Suberic acid (C₈). Error bars represent the standard deviation of three replicates.

Dust film mass dependence

Figure S. 2 Total mixing ratios as a function of dust film mass for each DCA.

Table S 3: List of all gas phase m/z found for the PTR-ToF operating on H₃O⁺ mode, depicting in which experiments each of them was produced. Markings in bold indicate the experiments in which the respective ion relative abundance was ≥ 5%. Formula assignment was based on literature (Buhr et al., 2002; de Gouw and Warneke, 2007; Yuan et al., 2017 and references therein) and some standards fragmentation patterns performed.

<i>m/z</i>	Formula	Suggested source/product	Succinic (C ₄)	Glutaric (C ₅)	Adipic (C ₆)	Pimelic (C ₇)	Suberic (C ₈)
31.018	CH ₃ O ⁺	methanal	v	v	v	v	v
33.033	CH ₅ O ⁺	methanol		v			
41.039	C ₃ H ₅ ⁺	alcools, etc		v	v	v	v
43.018	C ₂ H ₃ O ⁺	acetone, acetic acid, ...	v	v	v	v	v
43.054	C ₃ H ₇ ⁺	[butanoic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O - CO		v	v	v	v
45.033	C ₂ H ₅ O ⁺	acetaldehyde H ⁺	v	v	v	v	v
47.011	CH ₃ O ₂ ⁺	formic acid H ⁺	v	v	v	v	v
55.054	C ₄ H ₇ ⁺	[butanal H ⁺] - H ₂ O		v	v	v	v
57.033	C ₃ H ₅ O ⁺	[propanoic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O	v	v	v	v	v
57.069	C ₄ H ₉ ⁺	alcohols, vocs...	v	v	v	v	v
59.011	C ₂ H ₃ O ₂ ⁺	malonic, succinic...	v				
59.049	C ₃ H ₇ O ⁺	acetone/propanal H ⁺	v	v	v	v	v
60.021	C ₂ H ₄ O ₂ ⁺			v			
60.047	C ₃ H ₈ O ⁺			v			
61.027	C ₂ H ₅ O ₂ ⁺	acetic acid H ⁺	v	v	v	v	v
69.033	C ₄ H ₅ O ⁺	[succinaldehyde H ⁺] - H ₂ O			v		
69.069	C ₅ H ₉ ⁺	[pentanal H ⁺] - H ₂ O , others	v	v	v	v	v
71.048	C ₄ H ₇ O ⁺	[butanoic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O		v	v	v	v
71.085	C ₃ H ₁₁ ⁺	[hexanoic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O - CO				v	v
73.027	C ₃ H ₅ O ₂ ⁺	malonaldehyde H ⁺	v	v	v		
73.065	C ₄ H ₉ O ⁺	butanal H ⁺	v	v	v	v	v
75.042	C ₃ H ₇ O ₂ ⁺	propanoic acid H ⁺	v	v	v	v	v
81.068	C ₆ H ₉ ⁺						v
83.084	C ₆ H ₁₁ ⁺	[hexanal H ⁺] - H ₂ O	v			v	v
85.027	C ₄ H ₅ O ₂ ⁺	[oxo butanoic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O		v			
85.065	C ₅ H ₉ O ⁺	[pentanoic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O		v		v	v
85.099	C ₆ H ₁₃ ⁺	[heptanoic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O -CO					v
87.044	C ₄ H ₇ O ₂ ⁺	succinaldehyde H ⁺	v	v	v	v	v
87.077	C ₅ H ₁₁ O ⁺	pentanal H ⁺		v		v	v
89.023	C ₃ H ₅ O ₃ ⁺	oxo-propanoic ac. H ⁺	v				
89.059	C ₄ H ₉ O ₂ ⁺	butanoic acid H ⁺		v	v	v	
97.063	C ₆ H ₉ O ⁺	[adipaldehyde H ⁺] - H ₂ O					v
97.098	C ₇ H ₁₃ ⁺	[heptanal H ⁺] -H ₂ O					v
99.079	C ₆ H ₁₁ O ⁺	[hexanoic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O				v	v
101.021	C ₄ H ₅ O ₃ ⁺	[succinic ac. H ⁺] - H ₂ O	v	v		v	
101.059	C ₅ H ₉ O ₂ ⁺	glutaraldehyde H ⁺		v	v	v	v
101.094	C ₆ H ₁₃ O ⁺	hexanal H ⁺					v
103.073	C ₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ ⁺	pentanoic acid H ⁺			v	v	
115.071	C ₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ ⁺	adipaldehyde H ⁺				v	v
117.090	C ₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ ⁺	hexanoic acid H ⁺				v	
131.100	C ₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ ⁺	heptanoic acid H ⁺					v

Surface products

Figure S. 3: Sorbed-Phase Products detected by UHPLC-MS analysis of (a) adipic acid (C₆) and (b) pimelic acid (C₇), and (c) suberic acid (C₈). The results for the irradiated samples are compared to the dark ones prepared the same day. When the same formula is mentioned more than one time, it represents isomers.